

THE MINISTER AND HIS HOME

Mutabazi Placide*^{1,2}, Sangwa Sixbert^{1, 3}, Niyitegeka Jean Pierre⁴

¹Open Christian University, South Africa

²Mount Kenya University, Rwanda

³Africa Leadership University, Rwanda

⁴University of Rwanda, Rwanda

*Email: muplacidus@gmail.com

Abstract: The home of the minister is very important to his ministry in many respects. The ability to manage his home alongside taking care of the Church is one of the qualifications Paul listed for Timothy in choosing bishops for the churches under his ministry (I Timothy 3:4-5). A wife that is spirit-filled and exercises some of the spiritual gifts of ministry would complement the ministry of her husband (Horrell, 2018). Children of the minister often become the yardstick of his effectiveness and ability to develop the character and behavior of his members (2 Corinthians 3:2).

This article qualitatively discusses the minister as a husband, his duty to his wife, his duty to his children, minister's wife, the minister's children and minister's accountability to God. The authors confirm that the home of the minister is very important to his ministry in many respects. Therefore, the minister, his home and the ministry cannot be apart.

Key word: God, Holy Spirit, Home, Minister, Ministry

1. INTRODUCTION

The home of the minister is very important to his ministry in many respects. The ability to manage his home alongside taking care of the Church is one of the qualifications Paul listed for Timothy in choosing bishops for the churches under his ministry was, “He must manage his own family well and see that his children obey him, and he must do so in a manner worthy of full respect. If anyone does not know how to manage his own family, how can he take care of God’s church?” (I Timothy 3:4-5). The home of the minister is very important to his ministry in many respects. He himself gets encouragement and support largely from his home, where his wife and children contribute to his physical, psychological, social and spiritual needs. His responsibilities for giving training and direction to the family cannot be left to chance because the physical, social and spiritual condition of his home and family follow his ministry in all directions.

2. THE MINISTER AND HIS HOME

This part discusses the minister as a husband, his duty to his wife, his duty to his children, minister’s wife, the minister’s children and minister’s accountability to God.

2.1 The minister as a husband

When God set up the ministry, He instructed the minister to discharge their family responsibilities as equally well as they ministered unto Him spiritually. Paul’s instruction to all believers in relation to their families is, “But if any provide not for his own, and especially for those of his own house, he has denied the faith, and is worse than an infidel” (I Timothy 5:8). For the minister to be the example that he must be, he should not forget to lead his household in the manner that is acceptable in biblical terms.

2.2 His duty to his wife

The duty of husband to his wife is well expressed in Genesis 2:23-24, “²³The man (Adam) said, “This is now bone of my bones and flesh of my flesh; she shall be called ‘woman, for she was taken out of man.” ²⁴That is why a man leaves his father and mother and is united to his wife, and they become one flesh. The basic need of every wife is LOVE from her husband, which should be expressed in patience, understanding, care, tenderness, cheerfulness, and encouragement. Deuteronomy 24:5 scripturally supports this attitude of the husband towards his wife “If a man has recently married, he must not be sent to war or have any other duty laid on him. For one year he is to be free to stay at home and bring happiness to the wife he has married”. Solomon had a lot of experience with women and advises the following in Proverbs 5:18” May your fountain be blessed, and may you rejoice in the wife of your youth”. The duty of the husband to his wife is also confirmed by Peter(I Peter 3:7)” Husbands, in the same way be considerate as you live with your wives, and treat them with respect as the weaker partner and as heirs with you of the gracious gift of life, so that nothing will hinder your prayers”. A good note of the husband’s love to his wife is stated by Paul in Colossians 3:19 ”*Husbands, love your wives and do not be harsh with them*”.

2.3 His duty to his children

The minister as a husband is obligated to love and provide for the needs of his children (II Corinthians 12:14) quoted”... After all, children should not have to save up for their parents, but parents for their children”. Husband should this in the way suggested in I Timothy 3:4” He must manage his own family well and see that his children obey him, and he must do so in a manner worthy of full respect”. In Proverbs 22:6, Solomon says, “Train up a child in the way he should go: and when he is old, he will not depart from it.” Children that are prayerful and knowledgeable in the Word of God are great assets to the minister. He should therefore teach them how to pray

and study the Word of God. They should be led to repentance and water baptism and be filled with the Holy Spirit.

2.4 The minister's wife

Just as the wife expects the husband to love her, so must she understand that marriage is a mutual bond between a man and a woman to support each other (Gorman, 2009). The support of the wife to her husband, the minister, is very important to the mental, emotional, and spiritual uplifting for effective ministry (Burrige, 2007). The wife that intercedes for the minister and the entire family and also teaches the children like Lois and Eunice did to Timothy would find love, peace, and joy (Gushee&Stassen, 2016). A wife that is spirit-filled and exercises some of the spiritual gifts of ministry would complement the ministry of her husband (Horrell, 2018). The life and ministry of the minister is so hectic that their wives will do them great service by being humble, obedient, encouraging, respectful, and serviceable towards them (Horrell, D.G., 2016).

2.5 The minister's children

Children of the minister often become the yardstick of his effectiveness and ability to develop the character and behavior of his members. This is confirmed in 2 Corinthians 3:2 "2 You yourselves are our letter, written on our hearts, known and read by everyone." Children should understand that their home and public life is a written epistle for the public to measure their father's ministry by (2 Corinthians 3:2).

2.6 Minister's accountability to God

The first area of accountability was to self. Yet it is impossible to truly be accountable to ourselves without divine assistance. When we come to God to answer for our failures and our sin,

we find He already knows everything that we have come to confess. “For your ways are in full view of the Lord, and he examines all your paths” (Proverbs 5:21). We can use the prayer of David in the time of self-examination and ask His help to see the areas of our lives that need to be changed. “Search me, O God, and know my heart; try me, and know my anxieties; and see if there is any wicked way in me, and lead me in the way everlasting” (Psalm 139:23-24). If we solely examine our hearts without God’s aid, our heart will deceive us. This is also stated in Jeremiah 17:9-10:” The heart is deceitful above all things, and desperately wicked; who can know it? I, the Lord, search the heart; I test the mind, even to give every man according to his ways, according to the fruit of his doings”. Psalm 139:2-3 confirms that God knows all about us:” You know my sitting down and my rising up; you understand my thought afar off. You comprehend my path and my lying down, and are acquainted with all my ways”. In accepting that God knows all about us, one should admit that God understands us, fills us with grace, and deals with our sins covered in His mercy as written in Psalm 139:17-18:”How precious to me are your thoughts God! How vast is the sum of them! Were I to count them they would outnumber the grains of sand- when I awake, I am still with you”.

We will often fail in our efforts for accountability but will continually be offered grace to rise again and go forward in His mercy. “He has not dealt with us according to our sins, nor punished us according to our iniquities. For as the heavens are high above the earth, so great is His mercy toward those who fear Him” (Psalm 103:10-11).

3. CONCLUSION

The ability to manage his home alongside taking care of the Church is one of the qualifications Paul listed for Timothy in choosing bishops for the churches under his ministry(I Timothy 3:4-5). The home of the minister is very important to his ministry in many respects. He himself gets

encouragement and support largely from his home, where his wife and children contribute to his physical, psychological, social and spiritual needs. His responsibilities for giving training and direction to the family cannot be left to chance because the physical, social and spiritual condition of his home and family follow his ministry in all directions. The minister, his family and the church cannot be apart.

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